

The role and importance of Bahadir Jalolov's work in the development of the painting of Uzbekistan.

MAMATKULOV RASHIDBEK RAVSHANBEKOVICH

Kokan State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of "Fine art and engineering graphics"

ANNOTATION

The establishment of the Academy of Arts of Uzbekistan was of great importance in the development of visual arts in our country. Among other things, activities of the National Institute of Painting and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod, Scientific Research Institute of Art Studies, and Colleges of Painting and Design have been organized under this Academy. In addition, an art magazine is also active. It is known that in the National Institute of Painting and Design, in colleges of fine arts, education is provided in accordance with international requirements, mature personnel are trained, and they can mobilize their potential in bringing the art of Uzbekistan to a new stage.

Key words: St. Petersburg, Art Academy, painting, Kamoliddin Behzod, Repin, Chingiz Ahmarov, Alisher Navoi.

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People's artist of Uzbekistan - Bahadir Jalolov, laureate of the State Prize named after Alisher Navoi, is one of the talented artists contributing to the development of modern painting art. Bahadir Jalolov was born on May 27, 1948 in Tashkent. In 1968, he graduated from the P. P. Benkov State School of Art. 6 years later, in 1974, I.E. He also studied at the Faculty of Monumental Decoration of the St. Petersburg Institute of Painting, Sculpture and Architecture named after Repin. According to information, in his youth, he studied with the master of portrait art, Abdulhaq Abdullayev. In the first samples of the artist's creative activity, national feelings are expressed in different colors. The People's Artist of Uzbekistan continued his studies in fine arts and later learned the secrets of fine arts from Chingiz Ahmarov, Rozi Choriyev, Milnikov, Korolyov.

That is why the high skill is clearly visible in the portraits created by him. It is also said that the harmony of emotions in the artist's work makes fans fall in love with him. For example, the composition "Birth of Dance" not only glorifies Uzbek dancers, but shows sincere respect and love for them. Bahadir Jalolov achieved many achievements in the art of portraiture. The image of the favorite children of the Uzbek people is expressed in his full-fledged works. In this place, especially, the figure of great figures such as the academic artist Orol Tansikboyev, the great scientist, academician Vahid Zohidov, the famous artists of art Kamil Yormatov, Malik Qayumov, Muhyiddin Rahimov, Hamro Rahimova, Akrom Toshkanboev, Damir Roziboev is an example of our word. The artist always strives to study the human personality, to feel it in all its aspects. In fact, as we have seen above, the main scope of Bahadir Jalolov's creative activity is focused on the image of people, that is, creating portraits.

In fine art, he enriches his world of color with new and new shades. Most importantly, another aspect of Bahadir Jalolov's maturity is that he is an artist who mastered Eastern and Western traditions, found the commonality in these traditions and managed to bring them to the surface. For this reason, it has attracted the attention of art lovers of foreign countries. In addition, Bahadir Jalolov decorates luxurious palaces and buildings in advanced countries of the world with his monumental panels.

The well-known scientist Tilab Mahmudov evaluated the work of the artist and said: "For Bahadur, the history of man and humanity was a puzzle. He tries to solve this puzzle, to find points of harmony between the history of his people and the history of humanity." In fact, the artist, as a broad-minded creator, strives to learn the secrets of man, the world, and the universe. In conclusion, regular study of the theory of visual activity is one of the main conditions for successful mastering of visual art education.

Only a student who has mastered the rules of painting can effectively engage in practical creativity. "Whoever imagines science without practice is like the pilot of a boat setting out to swim without an oar, and he is never quite sure where he is going," said Leonardo da Vinci. Especially in the field of painting, practice must always be carried out in connection with a strong theory, without which nothing can be achieved. The history of fine arts has a great methodological experience in the practical study of painting. The significance and place of Bahodir Jalolov's work in the development of color painting in our country is that every work of art created with the magic of a brush has a formal meaning. In one of the paintings from the State Museum of History and Culture of Andijan, the image of a praying woman is depicted in gold. We can easily say that the artist really made a great contribution to the color art of Uzbekistan through such paintings.

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Bahadir Jalolov (1948.27.5, Tashkent) is a painter, People's Artist of Uzbekistan (1992), Uzbekistan (1997) and Kyrgyzstan (1998), I. Repin Institute of Painting, Sculpture and Architecture graduated (1974). Teacher at Tashkent Institute of Theater and Fine Arts (1974-80); Since 1997, the head of the prestigious painting workshop at the National Institute of Painting and Design, prof. (2000). Chairman of the board of the Union of Artists of Uzbekistan (1987-92). He started his work by creating portraits.

In his portraits, situations that give an idea of people's profession are reflected, the creative work process, deep psychological state are skillfully shown ("Architect",

1972; "Maskharaboz Akrom Yusupov", 1974; "Autoportrait", 1975; "Potter Woman. People" Master Hamro Rahimova, 1977, Memory of Artist Sh. Rahimov, 1980. 70's From the end of the 1980s to the beginning of the 1980s, he works effectively in the field of magnificent painting:

His murals on the opposite musical drama theater building, the lobby of the Chimyon sanatorium kitchen (1981), and the Cinema House in Tashkent (1982) introduced the artist as an artist whose face is sought after and who created a unique style. "Birth of Dance" (1982) for the foyer of the "Bahor" concert hall, for the wall of the Tallimarjon pump station club in the Kashkadarya region (1983), for the foyer of the Ko'kan Theater 17 (1987), for the school building in Khojand, Tajikistan (1988) , "Kortreik 200" (1990) in Kortrijk, Belgium, murals, landscapes for the Turkestan Palace in Tashkent ("Dreams of Omar Khayyom", 1993) and others ("Spring in Isfarada", "Mountain Village. So' qmoq", "Old Gurzuf Street", etc.), illustrations created for books (the works of Navoi, T. Tula, U. Nasir, etc.), easel paintings ("Afghanistan - 83", "Morning of Afghanistan » and b.) is the author.

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